

Cinderella to Cyberella: Transforming Women Through ICT

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Introduction

Women are seen as Cinderella all over the world whose major role was taking care of the house hold. Information and communication technologies can be powerful tools for advancing economic and social development through the formation of new sorts of economic activity, employment openings, improvements in health-care delivery and other services, and the augmentation of networking, participation and advocacy within society. Poverty, illiteracy, lack of computer literacy and language barriers are among the factors impeding access to ICT infrastructure, especially in developing countries. Another hindrance pertains to ICT is lack of its access to women. Women empowerment commonly refers to the process by which women augments their power to take control over decisions that shape their lives, including in relation to access to resources, partaking in decision making and control over distribution of benefits. Women's status can be related to certain components like, women's sense of self-worth; their right to have and to decide choices; their right to have access to chances and resources; their right to have the power to control their own lives, both within and outside the home; and their aptitude to influence the direction of social conversion to create a more just social and economic order, nationally and universally.

More women are convoluted in careers in the communications sector, but few have achieved positions at the decision-making level or serve on governing boards and bodies that sway media policy. The lack of gender sensitivity in the media is shown by the failure to eradicate the gender-based stereo typing that can be found in public and private local, national and international media organizations. The unremitting projection of negative and degrading images of women in media communications, electronic print, visual and audio - must be altered. Print and electronic media in most countries do not offer a balanced picture of women's lives and contributions to society in a varying world. Women are exposed to great discrimination in economic, education, health and social services access world wide. On the other hand the range of women's economic activities in emerging countries is very broad. It embraces formal sector and

informal sector employment, as well as self-employment in farming, trading and crafts production etc. There are plentiful possibilities for ICTs to improve women's economic activities in the field of trade, governance, education, health, crafts, employment in formal as well as informal sector. ICT brings lot of openings to women in the work situations and small business. Teleporting, flexi time and work from home arrangements are some of the gender magnitudes of ICT's usages.

This paper looks at the prospects generated by ICT supported networking processes for women's empowerment. It discusses the foremost challenges and hindrances confronted by women and recommends strategies to address those challenges and means to revamp the situations giving rise to women's empowerment

Why Do Women Need ICT?

Any technology that is not productive for women is not considered appropriate technology. In the past few years, communication technologies have been put to utilize in a number of educational and developmental applications. The national policy on education, observes that modern communication technologies have the potential to bypass numerous stages and sequences in the process of development. By doing so, the restraints of time and distance become manageable simultaneously. Looking at the previous days we find that there are numerous schemes to help women and girls to discover their potential and come out of their shackles. Information networks covering the entire country offer wide coverage. In most of the other ICT initiatives that depend on print media, Internet kiosks, portals, call centers, mobile, video digital photography etc, there is not desirable access and use by women. Information needs of women in the new global environment is as diverse as the socio-economic scenario. Considering women as a monolithic group will over simplify their information needs. Within women's group itself, globalization has generated the haves and the havenots to those who are in a valuable position due to globalization and those relegated further into disadvantaged position under the new economic policy. The information needs will also vary accordingly. Within women's group itself, the needs fluctuate accordingly. Urban educated women need information on educational & research opportunities, career advancement facilities, employment prospects in India and abroad, fashion and market values, health and child care facilities, art and entertainment, social support system for working women, legal rights and provisions. Urban lower middle class women need information on educational facilities and opportunities, career advancement and job opportunities, inexpensive health and childcare, inexpensive social support systems, legal rights and provisions against social injustice, domestic violence. Poor urban women may need information on, free health services and child care facilities, job opportunities in the low paid informal sector including domestic services, housing availability specially in slums, free educational facilities, information regarding government programmes.

ICT can play a foremost role in women empowerment. But this cannot occur till the e-governance and ICT strategies and policies become transparent and accountable. To orient ICT projects, ICT project planning and implementation for social development and gender equality must take place in a context which comprises of some components like;

1. Creating an environment which supports and inspires strategies to endorse women's equal access to and opportunity to benefit from ICT projects
2. Developing content which speaks to women's concerns and replicates their local knowledge, and which is of value for their daily lives, business enterprises, and family responsibilities
3. Supporting representation of women and girls in scientific and technical education, and using ICTs to promote their participation in education at all levels
4. Promoting employment in the IT sector for women.
5. Executing e-governance strategies which are accessible to women.

How to Empower Women Through ICT

A nation that wishes to progress cannot afford to disregard capacity building and empowerment of women. Gender sensitivity is the precondition that must prevail and be strengthened at all levels. Women's development is now indispensably associated with technology. Thus, technological intervention undertakes a greater and more vital role, especially when viewed globally with respect to women's sustainable progress. Women should build for themselves a new identity and a more honorable place in society. As has been experienced the world over, women have restricted access to technologies in India. However, there are innumerable incidents to prove that when women are trained, they show noteworthy understanding and control in using technologies commendably. In India, women comprise a large portion of the rural population and play a significant role in the rural sector. Their involvement in a number of productive actions is commonly overlooked. The knowledge networking processes with the inception of ICT and convergence technologies, is possible to bring up a significant fraction of women communities in digital network which focuses on localized information and customized solutions, and works on the theme of global technologies for local use. Women, however, are still very much in a minority among the beneficiaries of knowledge networking. Women still face huge imbalances in the ownership, control and regulation of these new information technologies.

Governments and civil society organizations have still not entirely absorbed the comprehensive potential of ICT in gender development and therefore are far from the stage of generating enabling frameworks and spaces for the growth of engendered ICT -models access issues: The new technology comes at a financial cost, which makes access difficult especially for rural women. The difficulty is compounded by the fact that women in developing countries have little control over the household income and do not have the decision-making power to capitalize in these technologies. The availability of ICT in these countries is therefore skewed towards the urban areas and women in rustic areas constitute one of the main marginalized groups. Capacity and skillsinstigating knowledge networking processes and benefiting from them requires a level of capacity and trained human resource power. Women because of their backward positions are at deprived position than men to fully benefit from knowledge networking. Poor language skills also pose a hurdle for women to access these networks. This makes the combination of local knowledge of women with the universal knowledge, a difficult task. Then how to empower women in ICT usage is a question.

ICT strategies and models can succeed in linking the gap only if there is a continuous effort towards designing of policy frameworks and avenues which may create opportunities and incentives for women to partake and profit from the networking processes. Women should be empowered by enhancing their skills, knowledge and access to information technology. This willstrengthen their ability to combat negativeportrayals of women internationally and to challenge instances of abuse of power of an increasingly important industry.

The starting point for any efficacious gender-entrenchedknowledge networking approach is the development of relationships with the society. Women must talk about their needs, share information, and work together. This is where the intercessor organizations can offer a platform for women to get energetically involved within the processes. The ownership of ICT for the majority of women in emerging countries is not viable. The question of how women can gain access to ICT becomes essential to the knowledge networking processes. Intermediary organizations can confirm that e-mail accounts, bulletin boards, search engines, mailing lists, list serves and other suitable functions serve as communication, networking and collaboration channels among the women's group, and between women and the external sphere. They could also contribute to building capacities of women by providing basic computer abilities, Internet andaccess to information

via Internet, desktop publishing, and e-commerce. ICTs are potentially an important knowledge resource for women. We need also to consider what kind of information is being accessed? We need to view women not as passive recipients of information, but active knowledge and technology developers.

ICT Related challenges Faced by Women: Strategies

Women are largely under represented in the global technology arena. Women need mentors, role models and strong networking opportunities. ICT project planning and implementation for social development and gender equality must take place in a context which consists of the strategies;

1. An environment which supports and encourages strategies to promote women's equal access to and opportunity to benefit from ICT projects has to be created and a regulation and policy environment which supports women's use of ICTs has to be enabled
2. Content which speaks to women's concerns and reflects their local knowledge, and which is of value for their daily lives, business enterprises, and family responsibilities has to be developed (c) Increased representation of women and girls in scientific and technical education, and using ICTs to promote their increased participation in education at all levels has to be supported
3. Increased employment in the IT sector for women and the use of ICTs for women's SMEs has to be promoted
4. Implementing e-governance strategies which are accessible to women have to be implemented
5. Women's lobbying and advocacy activities have to be promoted

The advent of ICT has changed the global scenario and many unexplored areas are now open for encashment. It is for the women community to utilize the benefits to the maximum possible extent. The best part about ICT is that it is capable of various adjustments as per the requirements of the segment who use it. It should be understood that ICT can be adjusted as per the needs and requirements of women too. It is simple that it can be operated from every home irrespective of its location. This means that even the traditional and orthodox families can allow the women to participate and use ICT from their respective homes. In India there is an abundance of "women entrepreneurs" who are capable of making their mark at the global level. However, the awareness and facilities to these women are missing drastically. The national policies and strategies have not yet considered this unexplored potential pool of intellectual inputs. With simple training and awareness programmes we can make a big difference in the lives of women.

In developing countries women are abused and are victims to various kinds of violence in almost all these sectors. Submissiveness and servility is in their nature because of the inequality they face. Despite the great progress of education in many countries, women are still not considered as equal gender in all spheres. The status of women is considered to be inferior to man even after her noteworthy contribution to society. Women should stand for themselves and demand that their voice be heard. Women empowerment is the urgent issue that has to be discussed. Various NGOs are working for the betterment of women and give them training for self-independence. Government is also taking this issue seriously and has announced various policies in favor of women. In this scenario Information and Communication Technology is also playing an important role. Through ICT women are getting security, awareness, knowledge, employment, confidence, etc. Ours is a male dominant society, so work done by women is never recognized and appreciated.

Suggestions

Women should be empowered by augmenting their skills, understanding and access to information technology. Women need to be involved in decision-making concerning the development of new

technologies in order to participate in sustainable development of the nation. Accessibility should be offered to women in order to derive the paybacks from applications like tele-education etc. It is needed that Multifunctional Converged Application Community Centers (MCACs) should facilitate the Telecommunication services. Computing services like E-mail and Internet access, information about local data base and generating awareness about governments' programmes should be introduced. NGOs and the government should come together to make alleviation programmes popular through women centric initiatives. Community networking may offer many profits to the world. It is true that rural ICT projects that seek to bring emerging technologies like low cost computing and internet access to rural areas, social institutions and governments are growing fast. There is no common design for rural ICT networks because communities vary in social, economic, and political outfit, and therefore information needs, and the design of community networking system, will also vary. For fruitful community networking, the design and implementation of projects should be driven by the explicit needs of communities. Monitoring of women's adoption of the ICT facilities is the need of the hour.

Conclusion

ICT is a growing sector that creates more than 120,000 new jobs every year. Women are still under-represented in this sector. Information needs of women as well as their ICT use differ widely. Those trying to install ICTs for women empowerment should build their strategies grounded on ICT use pattern and varied information needs of rural women. Creating a dynamic and relevant content for rural women continues to remain as a major challenge. There is a gender gap within what we call the digital revolution. Adequate resources need to be allocated for this activity. The advent of ICT has altered the global scenario and many unexplored areas are now open for encashment. It is for us and especially women to exploit the paybacks to the maximum possible extent. Cinderellas would be empowered to become Cyberellas. There is an increasing demand for digital skills and higher qualifications across a wide variety of sectors for women. The under-representation of women in ICT shows a waste of highly qualified resources which can threaten the economic development of the nation.

The ICT has a potential to bring development for a nation. It can reduce trade distortions, eliminate poverty, empower weaker segments including women, etc. The same is, however, possible only if a nation follows sound ICT strategies and policies which are accessible for both men and women. We have to set our priorities to those areas where we are lagging far behind. One such area is the unequal access of ICT to women. Despite economic and socio-cultural barriers to women's use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), if women are able to use them productively, they can substantially improve their lives and increase their income. The future for women has to be reshaped by providing them technology based education. Harnessing ICT to advance gender equality is not only vital for women empowerment but critical to sustainable development. It is estimated that 90% of future jobs will require ICT skills. Women's digital inclusion is key to sustainable economic growth. We need to teach the skills that women of all social classes need to take full advantage of ongoing technological advances. Women must be informed about the opportunities posed by technology and ICTs, so they are empowered to demand greater access.

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